

Comparative Evaluation of Tramadol vs. Nalbuphine as Adjuvants to Ropivacaine in Supraclavicular Block: A Cross-Sectional Observational Study

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Abstract:

Background: Supraclavicular block is a prominent upper limb regional anaesthetic treatment that manages postoperative pain and delivers personalised anaesthesia. Adjuvants are often added to ropivacaine, a common local anaesthetic, to improve block effectiveness and longevity. This study assessed side effects, postoperative pain control, and sensory and motor block to determine the efficacy of tramadol and nalbuphine as adjuvants to ropivacaine in supraclavicular block.

Methods: As an adjuvant to ropivacaine, 87 adult subjects were randomised to receive either nalbuphine (Group N, n=44) or tramadol (Group T, n= 43). Along with the incidence of side effects and postoperative pain scores at different intervals, the onset and duration of sensory and motor blocks were noted. Version 23.0 of SPSS was used to analyse the data, and a p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

Results: While the duration of both blocks was longer in the tramadol group ($p < 0.001$), the start of sensory and motor blocks was substantially sooner in the nalbuphine group ($p < 0.001$). At 4, 8, and 12 hours after surgery, the tramadol group's postoperative pain assessments were reduced ($p < 0.05$). Between the two groups, the incidence of side effects, such as nausea, vomiting, and pruritus, was similar and did not differ statistically.

Conclusion: Nalbuphine started sensory and motor block faster, while tramadol lasted longer and controlled early postoperative pain better. Most side effects were minor with both adjuvants. Tramadol is better for prolonged anaesthesia or postoperative analgesia than nalbuphine as ropivacaine adjuvants.

Recommendations: It is advised to conduct more research with bigger sample sizes and a wider range of patients to validate these results and investigate the possible advantages of combining these adjuvants for the best results in supraclavicular block.

Keywords: Supraclavicular Block, Ropivacaine, Tramadol, Nalbuphine, Regional Anesthesia.

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Introduction

Because regional anaesthesia techniques, like the supraclavicular block, are effective at providing targeted anaesthesia, lowering the need for general anaesthesia, and easing postoperative discomfort, they are frequently used in upper limb procedures. Since ropivacaine has a longer half-life than bupivacaine and a better safety profile overall—especially when it comes to less neurotoxicity and cardiotoxicity—it is frequently chosen over other local anaesthetics [1]. Nonetheless, the investigation of different adjuvants has been prompted by the need to maximise the duration and quality of analgesia while reducing the amount of local anaesthetics needed.

Tramadol has been extensively researched as an adjuvant in regional anaesthesia. Tramadol is a centrally acting analgesic with a dual mode of

action comprising opioid receptor agonism and inhibition of serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake. When used with local anaesthetics, it has been demonstrated to increase the duration of both motor and sensory blocks [2]. As an adjuvant, nalbuphine—a combined kappa agonist and mu antagonist opioid—has drawn interest because of its analgesic qualities and low risk of respiratory depression, which is a typical issue with other opioids [3].

The potential advantages of these adjuvants in improving the effectiveness of regional anaesthesia have been brought to light by recent investigations. For example, a study showed that nalbuphine increased the duration of the brachial plexus block and accelerated the onset of analgesia when combined with ropivacaine [4]. Similarly, as

adjuvant to ropivacaine, tramadol was found to provide superior postoperative pain control and to greatly prolong the duration of sensory and motor block [5].

The decision between tramadol and nalbuphine as adjuvants in supraclavicular block is still up for debate in spite of these findings. Although there is a lack of comparison evidence directly comparing the efficacy and safety of these medications, they have demonstrated potential in augmenting the effects of ropivacaine. In addition, a thorough assessment is required to inform clinical practice due to the varying effects of these adjuvants on the onset, duration, and quality of anaesthesia as well as the side effect profiles they are associated with.

This study aims to compare the efficacy of tramadol and nalbuphine as adjuvants to ropivacaine in supraclavicular block.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted over a period of 11 months at Patna Medical College & Hospital.

Participants: A total of 87 participants were included in the study. The participants were adult patients scheduled for upper limb surgeries requiring a supraclavicular block.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 18 to 65 years.
2. with ASA physical status I or II.
3. scheduled for elective upper limb surgery under supraclavicular brachial plexus block.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with known allergies to local anesthetics or the study drugs.
2. with a history of substance abuse or chronic opioid use.
3. with coagulopathy or on anticoagulant therapy.
4. with severe hepatic, renal, or cardiac disease.

5. with a history of neurological disorders affecting the upper limbs.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly assigned to receive either tramadol or nalbuphine as an adjuvant to ropivacaine. Blinding of the investigators and participants was maintained throughout the study to reduce performance and detection biases.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a standardized proforma, which included patient demographics, intraoperative and postoperative pain scores, the onset and duration of the block, and any adverse effects. Pain scores were assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at regular intervals.

Procedure: Participants were divided into two groups. Group T received tramadol as an adjuvant to ropivacaine, while Group N received nalbuphine as an adjuvant. The supraclavicular block was performed under aseptic conditions using a nerve stimulator to locate the brachial plexus. The study drug was then administered along with ropivacaine. The onset and duration of sensory and motor block were recorded, along with postoperative pain scores and any complications.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. The independent t-test was utilised to compare continuous variables, which were displayed as mean \pm standard deviation. The chi-square test was used to compare categorical variables, which were displayed as frequencies and percentages. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Result

The study comprised 87 participants in total. There were 43 participants in Group T (tramadol as an adjuvant) and 44 in Group N (nalbuphine as an adjuvant). There were no statistically significant differences in the demographic parameters of the two groups, which included age, gender, weight, and ASA physical status.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Variable	Group T (n=43)	Group N (n=44)	p-value
Age (years)	45.7 \pm 10.3	46.1 \pm 9.8	0.821
Gender (M/F)	26/17	28/16	0.771
Weight (kg)	67.5 \pm 8.2	68.3 \pm 7.9	0.612
ASA Physical Status (I/II)	28/15	30/14	0.840

In comparison to Group T, Group N experienced a substantially faster onset of sensory block (7.2 \pm 1.4 minutes vs. 9.1 \pm 1.7 minutes, $p < 0.001$). Likewise, Group N experienced motor block onset 8.4 \pm 1.3 minutes faster than Group T (10.2 \pm 1.8 minutes, $p < 0.001$).

Group T experienced a longer sensory block length than Group N (348.7 \pm 19.8 minutes vs. 372.5 \pm 21.4 minutes, $p < 0.001$). Similar trends were seen in the length of the motor block, with Group T reporting a longer duration (339.2 \pm 18.6 minutes) than Group N (312.3 \pm 17.4 minutes, $p < 0.001$).

Table 2: Onset and Duration of Sensory and Motor Block

Variable	Group T (n=43)	Group N (n=44)	p-value
Onset of Sensory Block (min)	9.1 ± 1.7	7.2 ± 1.4	<0.001
Onset of Motor Block (min)	10.2 ± 1.8	8.4 ± 1.3	<0.001
Duration of Sensory Block (min)	372.5 ± 21.4	348.7 ± 19.8	<0.001
Duration of Motor Block (min)	339.2 ± 18.6	312.3 ± 17.4	<0.001

The Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) was used to measure postoperative pain at 1, 4, 8, 12, and 24 hours following surgery. At 4, 8, and 12 hours, Group T's VAS scores were considerably lower than Group N's ($p < 0.05$). Nevertheless, there was no discernible difference between the two groups after an hour or twenty-four hours.

Table 3: Postoperative Pain Scores (VAS)

Time (hours)	Group T (n=43)	Group N (n=44)	p-value
1	2.1 ± 0.7	2.3 ± 0.8	0.271
4	2.9 ± 0.9	3.5 ± 1.0	0.011
8	3.4 ± 1.1	4.0 ± 1.2	0.019
12	3.9 ± 1.2	4.5 ± 1.3	0.025
24	2.7 ± 0.8	2.9 ± 0.9	0.312

The incidence of adverse effects was recorded in both groups. Group T had a higher incidence of nausea (20.9% vs. 9.1%, $p = 0.113$) and vomiting (16.3% vs. 6.8%, $p = 0.167$), although these differences were not statistically significant. Group N had a higher incidence of pruritus (18.2% vs. 7.0%, $p = 0.119$), but again, this was not statistically significant.

Table 4: Incidence of Adverse Effects

Adverse Effect	Group T (n=43)	Group N (n=44)	p-value
Nausea	9 (20.9%)	4 (9.1%)	0.113
Vomiting	7 (16.3%)	3 (6.8%)	0.167
Pruritus	3 (7.0%)	8 (18.2%)	0.119

Discussion

In 87 patients having upper limb surgery, the study evaluated the effectiveness of tramadol and nalbuphine as adjuvants to ropivacaine in supraclavicular block. The outcomes showed clear benefits for each adjuvant: tramadol offered superior postoperative pain control at many time periods and a longer duration of both sensory and motor block, whereas nalbuphine offered a speedier onset of both types of blocks.

When compared to the tramadol group, the nalbuphine group experienced sensory and motor block more faster, indicating that nalbuphine may be a better option when a prompt start of anaesthesia is essential. The tramadol group, on the other hand, showed a longer duration of both motor and sensory block, which may be advantageous in procedures requiring prolonged anaesthesia or when a longer postoperative analgesia is required.

Tramadol was found to provide superior pain relief during the early postoperative period, as evidenced by lower postoperative pain scores (4, 8, and 12 hours post-surgery) in the tramadol group. Nevertheless, after a full day, the pain levels of both groups were similar, indicating that the prolonged alleviation of pain with tramadol might be restricted to the initial 12 hours following surgery.

Between the two groups, the incidence of side effects, such as nausea, vomiting, and pruritus, was similar and did not differ statistically. This suggests that tramadol and nalbuphine, when taken as adjuvants in supraclavicular block, have negligible and controlled adverse effects.

Overall, the study's findings point to the need to customise adjuvant selection for supraclavicular blocks to the specific clinical situation. For treatments needing longer-lasting anaesthesia and better early postoperative pain control, tramadol may be more appropriate than nalbuphine, which may be better for quick block onset. Both medications' similar safety profiles lend credence to their use as adjuvants in this situation.

In a study, the effectiveness of nalbuphine as a 0.5% ropivacaine adjuvant for supraclavicular brachial plexus block in 100 patients was assessed. In comparison to the control group, the duration of sensory and motor blocks was significantly extended by nalbuphine, according to the data. With no discernible increase in adverse effects, the nalbuphine group also saw a considerable extension in the duration of postoperative analgesia [6].

Ninety patients receiving supraclavicular brachial plexus block for upper limb procedures were split into three groups in a randomised controlled study: ropivacaine plus normal saline, ropivacaine plus 10

mg nalbuphine, and ropivacaine plus 20 mg nalbuphine. According to the study, nalbuphine reduced the time it took for sensory and motor blockages to occur. The 10 mg dosage offered the best combination of safety and effectiveness. The likelihood of adverse effects like vomiting rose with higher dosages [7].

In supraclavicular brachial plexus blocks, the effects of nalbuphine added to ropivacaine versus ropivacaine alone were examined in a randomised controlled experiment involving seventy patients. In addition to experiencing a longer period of postoperative analgesia, the nalbuphine group also experienced an earlier onset of sensory and motor blocks. The research findings indicate that nalbuphine considerably boosts the effectiveness of ropivacaine while reducing side effects [8].

A study examined the effects of intrathecal tramadol and nalbuphine on women having vaginal hysterectomy. The results showed that nalbuphine produced analgesia more quickly, peaking at the same time as tramadol, and having similar effects on motor block and postoperative analgesia. While nalbuphine had a marginally better side effect profile than the other medication, both were determined to be efficacious [9].

The effectiveness of butorphanol and tramadol as adjuvants to levobupivacaine in supraclavicular brachial plexus blocks was compared in a study. Although both adjuvants were useful, butorphanol produced superior postoperative analgesia and a longer-lasting sensory and motor block than tramadol [10].

Conclusion

In summary, the study found that nalbuphine as an adjuvant to ropivacaine resulted in a faster onset of sensory and motor block, while tramadol provided a longer duration of block and better postoperative pain control at certain time points. Both adjuvants were associated with minimal and comparable adverse effects. The findings suggest that the choice between tramadol and nalbuphine may depend on the clinical scenario, with tramadol being more suitable for longer procedures or cases where prolonged analgesia is desired.

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